
**ENGINEERING INVESTIGATION OF THE TIANJIN CTF
FINANCE CENTRE IN TIANJIN, PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF
CHINA**

BY

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1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Tianjin Chow Tai Fook (CTF) Finance Center is a super-tall skyscraper in Tianjin, China. The tower is the second tallest building in Tianjin after Goldin Finance 117, eighth tallest building in the world, and the tallest building in the world with fewer than 100 floors. Construction started in 2013 and was completed in 2019.

Figure 1-1

Figure 1-2

1.2 Location

It is located at the intersection of the First Avenue and Xincheng West Road in the outer district of the Tianjin Economic-Technological Development Area.

1.3 Height, function and estimated cost

Tianjin CTF Finance Centre covers an area of 28,000 square meters, with a construction area of about 390,000 square meters. The total height of the tower is 530 meters, the height of the large roof structure is about 443 meters, the height of the core tube top is 471.5 meters, and the height of the crown steel structure on the top of the tower About 50 meters.

With 81 elevators, 97 floors above the ground and 4 floors underground, the skyscraper houses Class-A offices, 300 luxury serviced apartments, and a five-star, 350-room Rosewood hotel. The skyscraper has a commercial podium from negative 1st-5th floor, office towers from 7th-43rd floor, serviced apartments from 49th-70th floor and a hotel from 73rd-93rd floor. For the underground 4 floors, the main functions are civil air defense, parking garage (negative 2nd floor-negative 4th floor) and equipment room.

Its total cost is 8 billion Yuan (US \$1.2 billion).

Figure 1-3

Figure 1-4

2. Style of structure

2.1 Main structure

Tianjin Chow Tai Fook Financial Center is a polyline-shaped building with a square shape as the base, and the shape is tapered from bottom to top. In the design effect, in the daytime, the building will refract the sunlight to show various colours, and at night, the top of the inclined tower glows like a diamond. The new plan is rocket-shaped and dominated by arcs; the crown is like a cicada's wings.

The sleek tower's design synthesizes architectural, structural, and functional requirements. Square in plan, with rounded corners, the geometry maximizes the efficiencies of its three programmatic uses offices on the broad lower floors, serviced apartments in the shaft above and a luxury hotel in the tapering top floors arranged to match the optimum spans for each of these uses. With longer lease spans for the office floors, and shorter spans to maximize views at the apartment and hotel levels. The tower's curving facade is a result of techniques used to optimize structural efficiency. Its crystalline glass panels stretch from the lobby to the crown to give the building's integrated design a bold monolithic expression.

The curtain wall of gently curving glass conceals the innovative structural system of eight sloping columns that increase the structure's stiffness in response to seismic concerns and are integral to both the gravity and lateral systems. The sloped-column design proved not only faster to build than a conventional outrigger system, but also significantly reduced the construction cost from the amount of building materials needed to contribute to the environmental impact. This column design saved 19,000 tons of steel, 10,500 cubic metres of concrete and 3,900 tons of rebar. Multi-story wind vents combined with the tower's aerodynamic shape reduce vortex shedding, which in turn dramatically minimizes wind forces.

Figure 2-1

Figure 2-2

2.2 Foundation style

Tianjin CTF Finance Centre is L-shaped, with a length of 185 meters from north to south and a width of nearly 171 meters from east to west. The tower of Tianjin Chow Tai Fook Financial Center adopts pile raft foundation. The pile depth is 97.5 meters, the

effective pile length is 71.2 meters, and the design value of the vertical compressive bearing capacity of a single pile is 12,700 kN.

Figure 2-3

Figure 2-4

2.3 Wind and earthquake engineering

One of the main considerations for any super-tall tower is how it will resist wind forces. Powerful gusts of wind, reaching up to 100 miles per hour, can cause tall, slender buildings to sway. What's more, wind against the tower can create concentrated vortices that cause the structure to vibrate a phenomenon known as vortex shedding. Finding the right shape for the tower can dramatically reduce these forces. The team developed multiple variations of the tapered massing. Then, the design was put to an early test using a wind tunnel to study the effects of simulated atmospheric conditions. The wind tunnel testing helped the team make further refinements to the design: rounded corners, a scalloped building surface,

and a tapered crown. At the tower's apex, a porous design dramatically reduces wind acceleration.

Figure 2-5

Figure 2-6

In addition to wind forces, the team had to consider another significant risk: earthquakes. When building in an active fault zone, any structure especially a super-tall tower must be able to withstand both wind and seismic loads. Many towers of this size use supplemental bracing systems, called outriggers, to protect against the potential impact of an earthquake. But these systems can increase both building costs and construction time. Instead, SOM was able to devise an alternate solution a series of massive sloped columns, integrated with the tower's core, to make the whole structure resistant against lateral forces. The sloped-column design proved not only faster to build than a conventional outrigger system, but also dramatically reduced the amount of building materials needed. Compared

to a previous scheme created by another architect for the same project, SOM's final design saved 19,000 tons of steel, 10,500 cubic meters of concrete, 3,900 tons of rebar savings not only in construction cost, but also in terms of the building's environmental impact.

Figure 2-7

Figure 2-8

3. Construction procedures

3.1 Construction Process

- On November 20, 2009, Tianjin Chow Tai Fook Financial Center held a ground breaking ceremony. The then Tianjin Mayor Huang Xingguo attended the ceremony.
- The Tianjin CTF Finance Center was proposed as an idea in 2011.
- On May 17 2012, construction began.
- In April 2016, one third of the entire building had been built.
- In July 2016, the core tube of the building was poured to 260 meters.

- On August 3 2016, the height of the core tube exceeded 300 meters, becoming the “tallest building” in Tianjin Binhai New Area.
- In September 2016, the building was built as a transition truss between the office building and the serviced residential part.
- On December 15, 2016, the core structure of Tianjin CTF Finance Centre was successfully capped.
- In April 2017, CTBUH confirmed that the building has been structurally topped.
- In May 2017, the steel structure on the top of this building began to be installed.
- On July 29 2017, the horizontal structure inside and outside the core of the tower was capped and the tower crown construction stage was entered.
- On October 31 2017, the Tianjin CTF Finance Center tower crown was completed and successfully “coroneted.”
- On December 31 2018, Tianjin CTF Finance Center was officially lit.
- On August 19 2019, it passed the joint completion inspection.
- The building was completed in September 2019.
- On May 7 2020, the first floor office lobby and office area of Tianjin CTF Finance Center were handed over smoothly.

Figure 3-1

Figure 3-2

Figure 3-3

Figure 3-4

3.2 Companies involved

- Owner/Developer: Chow Tai Fook Enterprises
- Architect:
 - a. Design: Skidmore, Owings & Merrill LLP
 - b. Architect of Record: Ronald Lu & Partners; East China Architectural Design & Research Institute
- Structural Engineer:
 - a. Design: Skidmore, Owings & Merrill LLP
 - b. Engineer of Record: East China Architectural Design & Research Institute
 - c. Peer Review: Leslie E. Robertson Associates
- MEP Engineer:
 - a. Design: WSP
 - b. Engineer of Record: East China Architectural Design & Research Institute
- Project Manager: New World China Land Limited
- Contractor: China Construction Eighth Engineering Division
- Other Consultant:
 - a. Acoustics: Campbell Shillinglaw Lau Ltd
 - b. BIM: Syntegrate
 - c. Cost: Rider Levett Bucknall
 - d. Façade: Arup; Ronald Lu & Partners; Skidmore, Owings & Merrill LLP
 - e. Façade Maintenance: Arup
 - f. Interiors: Dreamtime Australia Design; Laguarda.Low Architects; Lim + Lu; AB Concept Limited; Make
 - g. Landscape: Plandscape Co., Ltd.; AECOM
 - h. LEED: WSP
 - i. Lighting: Brandston Partnership, Inc.; Isometrix Lighting + Design, Ltd.
 - j. Quantity Surveyor: Rider Levett Bucknall
 - k. Security: WSP
 - l. Traffic: Arup
 - m. Vertical Transportation: WSP
 - n. Wind: BMT Fluid Mechanics Ltd
- Material Supplier:
 - a. Aluminium: Guangdong JMA Aluminium Profile Factory (Group) Co., Ltd.

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- b. Ceiling: Armstrong Ceiling Solutions
 - c. Cladding: Dow
 - d. Façade Maintenance Equipment: CoxGomyl
 - e. Paint/Coating: Jotun

4. Structural measures of the building

4.1 Structural materials

A combination of materials like steel and concrete are used together in the main structural elements. The CTBUH database breaks out the materials used in the composite building's core, columns and floor spanning separately.

- Core: Reinforced concrete
- Columns: Concrete Encased steel
- Floor spanning: Steel
- Energy label: LEED Gold

The architects instead chose flat glass panels about 11,500 total from China Southern Glass (CSG Holding Limited). The vision glass comprises Insulated Glass Units with heat-strengthened, laminated, low-iron outer lites, a double-silver, low-e coating, and tempered, low-iron inner lites. Spandrel panels are made of low-iron laminated glass.

The use of flat glass panels meant that the designers had to get a bit more creative with the mullions to cover the doubly curved surfaces. They turned to an adaptable mullion system from Jangho, a major Chinese curtain-wall manufacturer, that could take over some of the formal gymnastics. In total, only 476 unique glass panel types were needed.

The design team also wanted to find a way to minimize the window-to-wall ratio to reduce solar gain and increase insulative value while still providing ample daylight. They ended up with V-shaped mullions that are almost 11 inches wide on the exterior and narrow to a much smaller profile on the interior.

The building's taper gave each floor a different shape; therefore, the exterior panels fit differently around every level, which meant that the mullions couldn't easily be arranged in perfectly continuous lines up the building. Rather than trying to approximate vertical stripes with the mullions, the designers staggered them to create a snakeskin-like effect that reads as organized but organic, a reflection of the flexible thinking required to erect this giant.

Figure 4-1

4.2 Structural design

The primary drivers of the tower's architectural and structural efficiency are the stepped, core-in-core system and the perimeter sloped column system. The core extending up through the residential zone was selected to be just large enough for the required architectural core elements: the residential core was extended through the office zone and an outer core was placed around the inner core with dimensions just large enough to accommodate the office core functions.

This concept, although very efficient architecturally, required intensive coordination between the architectural, mechanical, vertical transportation and structural teams in order to develop an efficient architectural plan that reconciled the MEP, vertical transportation, and structural requirements. This coordination effort resulted in a structure that has a consistent pattern of core openings with optimal link beam depths without compromising the architectural layout, ceiling height, and MEP services.

In the serviced apartment zone, wing walls were added to the hotel core creating an "egg-crate" structure that stiffened the core and created a smooth transition from the small to the large core. Apartment layouts were configured so that the wing walls are on apartment demising walls. The stepped, core-in-core system allowed the residential floor plate to be as small as possible, which both reduced the wind "sail" area and the seismic mass at the higher levels of the building.

Figure 4-2

Figure 4-3

Structural system

Figure 4-4

3 belt truss + 1 hat truss + tow crown

Figure 4-5

Figure 4-6

Figure 4-7

4.3 Strategy for structural system selection

The structural design of the building was developed on the basis of the targets of incorporating the principle of structural as well as architectural layout from the start of the design process, which included the following structural strategy:

- Pick and configure the structural tower framework for power, rigidity, cost-effectiveness, flexibility and build speed.

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- Use the latest technical developments in structural available materials on the local market, taking due account of the availability of local skilled workers and system of construction.
 - Control and locate the resistant gravity load mechanism to optimize its use in the resistance of lateral loads when harmonizing with the architectural design of apartments, commercial and hotel towers.
 - Integrate the new novelties in methods of research, architecture, materials, and construction.
 - Restrict the building movement (drift, acceleration, torsional velocity, etc.) to the requirements and norms agreed internationally.
 - Control the comparative displacement of the vertical parts.

5. Appraisal of structure rationality

The design of Tianjin CTF Finance Center is a comprehensive reflection of architectural, structural engineering and functional requirements being met. The building has an eye-catching slender body. The building is composed of a series of curves from bottom to top that converge on the tower crown. It stands elegantly on the skyline of Tianjin Binhai New Area. The graceful architectural shape leaves a deep impression.

Tianjin CTF Finance, located in Tianjin Binhai New Area, is 530 meters high, ranking the eighth tallest building in the world and the fourth tallest building in China. The project is designed by SOM Architects, RLP of Lu Yuanxiang Architects is responsible for the design, ECADI of East China Architectural Design and Research Institute is the responsible architect and engineer, and Arup is the technical consultant.

Tianjin Chow Tai Fook Financial Center covers an area of 28,000 square meters and has a construction area of about 390,000 square meters. It has refreshed the Chinese skyscraper building height ranking with a height of 530 meters. The 103-storey mixed-use building contains office floors, 300 serviced apartment units and a 350-room five-star hotel.

The building adopts a layered and gradually reduced floor slab design. The conical shape of the building is like a sharp sword piercing the sky. The design takes into account the aesthetics and is rich in visual impact, while greatly reducing the external wall surface area of the building. This novel design fully takes into account the resistance brought by the wind to the building in Tianjin Binhai New Area, and is more aerodynamic, which can effectively reduce the phenomenon of vortex divergence, minimize wind load, and reduce the exposure area of the building under sunlight and rain attack.

The total floor area was marginally only increased by 68m² and 87% of the building envelope surface is within 20 mm of the original design, preserving the authenticity of the architect's design. The building's aerodynamic shape greatly reduces vortex shedding by "confusing the wind" and disrupting the opportunity for any resonating wind forces and loads on the structure.

The building's façade is a visual expression of SOM's innovative design. In terms of appearance, the flat glass panel system and window frame system of the building follow the curve of the building's façade, highlighting the proportion of the tower's retracted portion, and at the same time subtly echoing the curvilinear and sloping structure, highlighting the visual dynamic of the building Vibrant appearance and connotation. The cascading glass curtain wall and crescent-shaped aluminium alloy frame reveal a unique and elegant architectural texture under the sunlight.

The building information modeling (BIM) technology of Yuanxiang Lv Architects reduces the construction time and engineering cost, and its crystal clear hyperboloid shape also reflects the outstanding contribution of digital design in optimizing the complex glass curtain wall structure. In Tianjin Chow Tai Fook Financial Center, it is estimated that at least 1,308 independent asymmetric IGUs (Insulating Glass Units, namely insulating glass modules) were manufactured for the facade curtain wall structure originally formed by the intersection of 8 irregular curved surfaces. After BIM analysis and repeated data modeling, the number of independent IGUs was reduced to 476 pieces, and an edge and corner segmentation method and dry-hanging curtain wall nodes for easy construction were proposed. The project was finally completed 4 months ahead of schedule. It can be seen that BIM had played a role in the optimization process critical use.

Lu Qingyao, Vice Chairman of RLP, said: "In the past few years, BIM has been widely used in the field of architecture, engineering and construction (AEC). The government introduced relevant standards and policies to strongly support the industry to accelerate its pace into the digital age. It is believed that in the future, BIM will integrate the advantages of departmental information resources, optimizing construction time and economic cost, and solving difficult structures will be more prominent. Tianjin Chow Tai Fook Financial Center, as a super high-rise building that attracts global attention, has a well-crafted appearance and reflects the "construction" throughout the process the art of making".

Figure 5-1

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